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Literature Review: Corporate Culture and Performance

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Abstract:

This study reviews research related to the relationship between corporate culture and performance. From previous studies, the author proposes research gaps that need to be carried out in the future, in the context of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises.

Keywords: *Corporate culture, performance.*

1. Introduction

The 4.0 revolution has been changing the landscape of many fields in many industries. The emergence of information technology promotes and enhances the close link between organizational culture and the operation of a business. However, building culture and ensuring business performance is a difficult problem, always needing to find the most suitable solution.

Today, organizations and businesses are constantly striving to achieve rapid growth, continuous improvement, preparation for the future and global integration (Salajegheh et al., 2015). Moreover, the constantly changing and difficult to predict working environment has posed many challenges to small, medium and large enterprises in Vietnam. These pressing problems cost organizations a lot of time and money to make changes to achieve to achieve peak performance. The traditional management model is not able to help businesses achieve high performance, prompting organizations to come up with new management methods (Taslimi, 2015). Therefore, in order to achieve high performance of the organization, it is necessary to identify the factors affecting the operation of the organization. In this regard, studies have shown that among the factors that can affect the performance of the organization is the organizational culture of the company (Irefin & Mechanic, 2014).

Current research exposes arguments and assumptions about how organizational culture relates to performance (Rose et al., 2008) and the likelihood of a relationship leading to a competitive advantage in a competitive marketplace. Kotter and Heskett (1992) found that organizational culture has a significant impact on performance over a period of time when key factors such as employees and customers are emphasized. Rashid et al. (2003) agree that employee commitment in the organization and customer loyalty are essential for the successful realization of organizational goals or objectives.

Culture can be a performance-enhancing factor, and culture can very well become a more important factor in determining a company's future success. In today's business environment, differentiation is moving from products and services to culture and talent/human resources. This type of move helps organizations gain competitive advantage through internal resources, rather than advertising or pricing as in the past. A significant aspect of internal resources includes employees. Jamieson (1983) identified organizational culture as the main differentiating factor in economic and organizational behavior across countries. Today, more empirical studies (Zhang et al., 2008) confirm the correlation relationship between organizational culture and performance. However, some of these studies failed to apply their findings across national borders. The goal is for an organization to gain competitive advantage through increasing employee performance and productivity by using an organizational culture that supports the organization's operations. Trefry, (2006) showed that companies that effectively develop their culture will most likely benefit from increased productivity and quality from their workforce and make their customers happy more loyal to them.

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Currently, Vietnam always ranks high in the list of leading textile and garment producing and exporting countries in the world. Recently, Vietnam's textile and garment products have received attention and become an alternative to Chinese products thanks to low labor costs, the signing of many multilateral free trade agreements. new,... That gave the textile and garment industry a lot of hope after the economy recovered from the crisis from the epidemic. In our country, with an effort to overcome many fluctuations of the Covid-19 pandemic, small, medium and large enterprises in the textile and garment industry have made strong and flexible changes and caught up with the needs of the era "moving from production of casual clothes to protective clothing", increasing labor productivity and creating a strong competitive advantage in domestic and foreign markets. Competitive advantage is a goal of business organizations and is a positive result of the relationship between organizational culture and performance, however, the differences depend on the research context. volatility (Wollard & Shuck, 2011). The in-depth study of organizational culture in many countries is the driving force for businesses to come up with appropriate solutions in the process of international integration.

The participation in the signing of many agreements such as CPTPP, EVFTA, FTA, ... optimally shows that our country is strongly integrating and opens up many opportunities for businesses to organize, break barriers and improve culture. organization. However, the fierce competition between businesses and organizations presents a difficult problem in terms of retaining talent and limiting brain drain. At the same time as the business expands into the "multicultural" market, the organizational cultural aspects will become the strength of the business. Many businesses could fall behind in this race if they do not adapt and innovate. So what is an effective solution for Vietnamese enterprises in the process of innovation and integration of the country?

In the context of developing countries like Vietnam, there are very few studies on this topic. In addition, new studies only stop at a certain industry without multi-sectoral analysis or testing of regulatory variables such as firm size or age of the enterprise.

2. Literature review

2.1. The relationship between organizational culture and creative organizational environment

The cultural development of the innovative and creative characteristics of the enterprise leads to the performance of the enterprise (Ogbonna and Harris, 2000), which suggests that attention should be paid to the innovation of the corporate culture. Not only that, the innovation of corporate culture thanks to the development of values and the impact of high-level incentives (Gil et al., 2018). Further, preserving a sustainable cultural culture in the direction of creativity and innovation will open up opportunities for the outstanding development of the organization. Research by Acar (2012) conducts analysis, empirical test, evaluation and shows that the cultural innovation of an enterprise depends on the importance of the leader. Their role greatly affects the development of strong and weak cultures in the enterprise, and is an important premise when developing work efficiency.

Financial culture is one of the central factors in decisions about the existence of an institution, especially in the fierce competition in the world financial markets (Warrick, 2017). "Culture is central to competitive advantage when it is different from other cultures and its constituents are difficult to imitate" (Ployhart, 2012 cited in Schneider, Ehrhart and Macey, 2013, p. 380). There are many factors affecting the traditional culture, but the traditional culture is a clear example in promoting, maintaining and evoking creativity in the traditional culture, especially the cultural culture emphasizes the role of the leadership model with the efforts to preserve the traditional culture. keep the culture (Warrick, 2017). Examining the impact of leaders in 32 business entities about a service in Greece on financial culture, (Simosi and Xenikou, 2010) concludes that managers allow subordinates to express opinions and actions in The working process will arouse in them an abundant source of motivation and a premise to promote creative passion for employees. These factors contribute to creating the foundation for the development of corporate culture and the foundation for positive values in the business. Research by Acar (2012) emphasizes the characteristics of corporate culture that are formed, developed and

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depend on the leadership style of the manager - including motivational activities, worthy rewards and the importance of managers affection between individuals. The reward system and diplomatic relations between leaders and employees have a large impact on the development of culture of two global automobile brands (Steers and Shim, 2013).

An organization's distinct culture creates a competitive advantage in the marketplace. Competitive advantage of enterprises and corporate culture owning relationship between interact with each other. Many studies have found common results in enhancing competitive advantage through corporate culture (Byrne et al., 2019). When an organization is made up of many managers interested in the process of building core values of the business, it will create a unique creative working environment, comprehensive innovation, and promote outstanding development. superiority of the enterprise (Barney, 1986) Then, corporate governance affects and creates a lasting competitive advantage for enterprises. In order for financial culture to create a competitive advantage for enterprises, it is imperative that the elements: "Valuable", "Distinctive innovation", "Cannot be copied" must exist in the financial culture. Creation and innovation of traditional culture is the environment suitable and best for the comprehensive development and increase of competitive advantage for enterprises, improving financial efficiency in both short and long term.

Based on the characteristics of the industry, in order to bring certain value and effectiveness in organizational activities, each specific industry and service needs to be suitable for a separate financial culture (Gordon, 1991). An example is that dynamism is not suitable for manufacturing industries, but the flexibility of health-related services will create a good culture for businesses. It proves that the external environment of the organization strongly influences the relationship between culture and performance. Discussing the cultural efficiency of a particular environment in many countries (Rose et al., 2008), research shows that the right cultural culture will support the promotion of the organic culture of a particular environment, but it does not work if it is applied. used in other circumstances. At the same time, the study shows that the culture with relationship is expressed in countries around the world, then, the study gives the assessment that the cultural efficiency of the cultural culture between countries is very strong if managers learn and integrate flexible core values and harmonize the behavior of employees from many different countries.

Studies on corporate culture and the role of culture in enterprises point to competitive advantages (Schneider et al., 2013). Faced with the constant fluctuations of the global economic market, the rapid integration of digital technology, the sense of organization's competitiveness development needs to come from the flexibility and creativity of the culture consistent with the leadership method and effectively applied to the continuous changes in each time of the business market (Block, 2003).

2.2. The relationship between organizational culture and dynamic competence

Teece, (2007) are the ones who have successfully proposed Resource-based Theory. Specifically, the appearance of dynamic arson and creative activities is an important factor for the formation and development of an organization's competitive advantage in the context of the fluctuating international market. Dynamic capacity can be the ability to combine or reuse and operate processes within the enterprise, creating a competitive advantage for the organization. However, this also means "the way things are done within the company, or what might be called current learning and practice models. In particular, corporate culture is considered an dynamic capacity (Barney, 1986 & 2011) and can promote enterprises to generate economic profits while maintaining competitive advantages in domestic and international arenas.

The "Resource-based Theory" by (Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000; Bledy and Ali, 2018) is said to have used the "Dynamic Capability Theory" as an advanced extension to make recommendations on benefits. Competitive advantage from an enterprise should be recognized in terms of functions, organizational processes, planning, management,... (Shuen and Sieber, 2009). Dynamic capacity is considered a competitive advantage, does not contain many organizational and management processes of the enterprise, and contains three key elements: coordination / integration, learning and complete formation (Teece, 2007). "Learning" is relevant to traditional culture, because learning is a journey "in essence social and collective and occurs as a result of a

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shared contribution to the understanding of complex issues” (Teece, 2007, pp. 520). At the same time, the learning curve can be described from the back-and-forth business conversations to derive key ideas and effective responses to a particular problem. Thereby, businesses can take advantage and promote competitive advantages from information processing, create effective solutions and strategies to handle difficulties that hinder their existence and competitiveness of the enterprise.

Through the activities of enterprises, organizational culture has a great influence on dynamic competence (Wagner, 1995), and is also a standard rule in the enterprise about employee behavior (Manetje & Martins, 2009). Financial culture has relationship with many different areas in the organization, directly affecting the increase of dynamic capacity based on core values and indirectly through human resources (Black, 1999). Not only that, organizational culture has a relationship with the development of human rights in the organization. Teamwork activities bring about employee development and relationship maintenance in an enterprise (Karia and Ahmad, 2006), the education, construction, cultivation and development of a corporate culture (Karia, 1999). . At the same time, group evaluations and rewards will bring about positive impacts, open employee motivation and improve labor efficiency (Ooi and Arumugam, 2006). Research in Arab banks, corporate culture has a positive relationship with employee engagement (Al Shehri et al., 2017). The positive influences in the relationship are: “Training and development; Organizational communication; Commendation and recognition”.

A firm's competitive advantage is developed from distinct cultural characteristics combined with corporate culture (Bogdanowicz, 2014). However, the benefits obtained from the corporate culture can only be achieved when there is a harmony and "match" between the strategy and the company's own culture. In contrast, Klein (2008) shows that this coincidence is not important for creating sustainable competitive advantage. By citing the demise of Enron, an American energy corporation, Klein demonstrates that creating a workspace embodies trust, unity, commitment, and discourages fear. then, financial culture plays an indirect role in creating tools in the development of competitive advantages. Customer orientation accompanied by creativity and increased labor efficiency needs to be flexible in organizations and differentiate itself from competitors in the market (Abdullah et al., 2014); (Szymańska, 2016) and Byrne, Dwyer and Doyle, 2019).

Based on the above studies, the study makes a claim about a strong link between corporate culture and dynamic capacity. Specifically, financial culture is a part of the dynamic capacity framework, supplemented and supported by the comments of Barney (2011), drawing out the financial culture as a source of competitive advantage for businesses, helping the organization to meet the conditions of the company. a holistic culture: valuable, unique creation, not easily copied.

2.3. The relationship between organizational culture and business performance

Along with the development of society, more and more rigorous arguments have been established about the relationship between financial culture and corporate governance (Schneider, Ehrhart and Macey, 2013). Studies by (Laforet, 2017; Omoregbe and Umemezia, 2017; Polychroniou and Trivellas, 2017) simultaneously confirm determine the existence of a two-way relationship between the financial culture and the corporate governance.

Culture in an organization needs to be maintained and constantly updated and renewed with the desire to promote cooperation in the enterprise (Murphy et al., 2013). At the same time, an increase in the level of interaction in the fields will bring good governance to the organization. (Ofori and Sokro, 2015) make an assertion about the core value in a company that needs to be better than the partner enterprise. This view is supported by Peter and Waterman (1982), who built corporate governance based on the level of social acceptance.

Based on the viewpoints, organizational culture contains factors that positively affect the operational efficiency of the organization, increase labor productivity and organizational effectiveness. Omoregbe and Umemezia (2017) points out effective leadership methods, continuous training of employees and building sound work processes. Thereby positively increasing the efficiency of the organization. Analysis of businesses

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choosing the Nigerian banking industry has shown a positive relationship between financial literacy and performance. Practice shows that corporate culture is the action orientation of enterprises, affecting the formation and development of business goals, especially in the decision-making process of leaders (Laforet, 2017; Omoregbe and Umemezia, 2017).). The conclusion shows that corporate culture contains management and leadership style, strategic goals, design process and business management, thereby confirming the impact on the company's reputation and corporate governance.

A strong culture is an important determinant of an organization's performance improvement and competitive advantage (Deal and Kennedy, 2000). A good culture has a positive relationship with organizational performance from market position, innovation, corporate performance and economic growth (Kipsang et al., 2015; Polychroniou and Trivellas, 2017). In contrast, all difficulties associated with a strong culture have an impact on the effective functioning of the organization, based on the difference of subculture values (Matthew, 2019). However, a major limitation from the study is that it does not cover all industries and regions around the world. The link between the financial culture and the operational efficiency is only an indirect impact, but does not fully reflect the financial activities of the enterprise. However, organizational culture is recognized as "the ability to promote learning and knowledge sharing" (Teece, 2007), and at the same time, it is responsible for attracting talent and creating soft skills suitable for the organization (Matthew, 2019). Many other scholars have also pointed out the bilateral relationship between visual culture and visual culture (Uddin and Hossain, 2012; Boyce et al., 2015; Nikpour, 2017).

In order to effectively develop an enterprise, excel in economic growth, and maintain a competitive advantage in the market, financial culture is a particularly important factor (Szymańska, 2016), and at the same time, corporate culture encourages enterprises to rise up. competition, diversification and integration of internal factors, making a difference in the production force, ... ensuring the maintenance of an organization, beyond the outstanding growth and development. . Financial culture is a distinct factor that distinguishes different organizations, and at the same time is a unique identity of businesses, related to innovation, change management, risk (Yilmaz and Ergun, 2008). Culture is represented by all the traditional values of the members of the organization. However, at present, corporate culture plays a more and more stable role in the face of the integration of digital data and modernization Schein (2010).

Viewed objectively, the operational efficiency of an enterprise is described as having achieved the objectives of the organization (Wei, Liu and Herndon 2011), and the operational efficiency reflects the effectiveness through management (Amin, 2017). To be sure, the relationship between corporate culture and loyalty is well established, and there are various links between culture and performance (Mariama-Zakari and Owusu-Ansah, 2013). An organization cannot underestimate financial culture including management, risk and behavior management, etc. From a macro perspective, the operational efficiency of an organization is extremely influenced by financial culture. The profitability of a business is influenced by the goals and aspirations of the organization, and at the same time reflects efforts to promote innovation and creativity, especially on the part of the enterprise (Oparanma, 2010).

In the context of global integration, in the face of "business challenges", business managers face many difficulties to survive and compete (Bolboli & Reiche, 2014). Difficulties include competition in increasing prices, difficulty in meeting market demand (Bolboli & Reiche, 2013). Companies and managers face many difficulties and obstacles in the process of building appropriate financial culture to improve corporate productivity (Kenny, 2012).

Profit is the decisive factor for an enterprise, and at the same time, expanding the scope and scale of the business is a practical job that directly serves to increase the production capacity of the enterprise. It is necessary to develop an effective and diverse financial culture when comprehensively considering the market challenges at the core of a group of companies rather than from one company (Lee & Bostots, 2013). Limited corporate integration with international culture is a huge barrier in the development process, and directly affects the valuation of enterprises and dividends of shareholders Idris et al (2015). Specifically, according to statistics, about 90% of companies with initiatives "have great difficulty" when they are not sensitive enough to integrate

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culture in the group of companies Bolboli and Reiche (2014). This difference is an existential barrier that directly affects the operational efficiency of enterprises (Weber & Tarba, 2012). Limited understanding of corporate culture is the cause of poor performance in corporate groups (Eaton & Kilby, 2015). At the same time, managers need to clearly realize the essential role of corporate culture to improve corporate governance (Viegas-Pires, 2013). In the process of exchanging between enterprises forming many groups, the lack or limitation of financial culture adversely affects business results and reduces the return of shareholders (Idris et al., 2015). About 72% of managers rate the role of financial culture in an important position in the business, 25% admit that a financial culture has a positive effect on the business Eaton and Kilby (2015). It can be said that business in general needs the synthesis and sensitivity of financial culture, if this factor lacks, it will lead to poor performance and gradually lose its position in the group of businesses (Eaton & Kilby, 2015; Viegas-Pires, 2013). This situation points to a problem in business: senior leaders need an effective corporate culture strategy to improve corporate governance (Hirsch, 2015).

The productivity of organizations in Nigeria is difficult in the banking sector due to a number of reasons: unclear vision, lack of direction, unfavorable social conditions, embezzlement, lack of innovation, limited communication vertical communication, poor inter-departmental linkage, lack of cooperation, limited idea management and expertise Ogbor (2012). Not only that, 2014 witnessed a severe oil price crisis that severely affected the banking sector here (Idris and Nayan, 2016), which led to a revenue deficit, a sharp decrease in bank deposits, unemployment and decline in trading volume (Osuma et al., 2019). Not only that, but statistics in the financial sector also show that “this institution recognizes prosperity in its unique cultural identity” (Omoregbe and Umemezia, 2017). The bank successfully built core values over many years in order to stay competitive and create excellent business performance Barney (1986; 2011). The purpose of the study also examines how financial literacy will affect the corporate governance of the organization in the context of Nigerian banks (in Lagos State).

Corporate culture has a positive effect on work performance. At the same time, formal culture has an essential place in the process of creating interpersonal connections and promoting quality work. According to Thompson & Luthans (1990), “Positive corporate culture will increase employee engagement, resulting in improved organizational performance, high consensus on strategic directions, and increased productivity. increased labor productivity, better decision-making”. “Corporate culture has a positive effect on business operation; With businesses with cultural characteristics that care about customers, shareholders and employees, business results will be more than expected and sustainable” - Heskett and Kotter (1992). Financial literature is used to evaluate the operational efficiency of enterprises, ensuring that when dynamic capacity increases, it will help the organization achieve stronger economic growth.

At the same time, corporate culture is linked to the corporate governance of the company. Research shows that corporate culture has a stronger association than corporate culture. At the same time, the study using samples from enterprises in Japan in the period 1987 - 2000 confirmed the power of corporate culture to affect employment, reward,... policies of Hirota et al. 2007). At the same time, the study shows that Japanese corporate governance is better and has a higher competitive advantage thanks to the value of corporate culture, along with that, corporate culture has a stronger impact than other factors such as corporate policies or corporate governance.

Traditional culture plays a particularly important role in the construction and development of corporate culture. There exist many studies on the importance of corporate culture to organizational culture (Denison & Neale, 1996).

The building and development of a strong culture has an influence on the corporate governance of an enterprise (Fey & Denison, 2003; Schein, 2010). Especially, according to Denison & Neale (1996), the criteria in the corporate governance are affected by the financial culture aspect. Leaders rely on factors to develop and spread organizational culture, solidifying the foundation of corporate culture to employees in the organization (Keyton, 2005).

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Financial culture has a role in increasing productivity and reducing risks from uncertain decisions (Wilkins & Ouchi, 1983). Building a strong organization requires an effective and relevant culture Gordon (1991). However, all construction orientations need to come from the specific characteristics of each field. Many surveys have been conducted on traditional culture by the National Institutes of Public Health in 40 countries to assess the extent of traditional culture. Five aspects of traditional culture were pointed out: respect, fairness, trust, pride, and close relationships. (Great Place to Work Institute, 2011). At the same time, the methodology is applied and gives the relationship between the financial culture and the corporate governance that interact with each other.

2.4. The relationship between innovation environment and business performance

The definition of corporate culture is simply understood as the "personality" of an organization, in which a comprehensive value system and beliefs, normative rules, behaviors, and methods of sharing knowledge within the enterprise. , ... creating a strong culture. A business with a strong culture will impact financial performance, increase effort and bring uniformity among employees, while aligning goals. Many studies have also shown that organizational culture increases productivity and inhibits hesitation, uncertainty, and uncertainty in decision making and the implementation of effective decisions (Wilkins & Ouchi, 1983).

The formation of specific resources of the enterprise has an impact on the development of the enterprise (Barney, 2011). But not all resources are decisive to increase the super profit for enterprises. The study shows that resources: Physical capital, machinery and technology are evaluated as strategic resources, which are applied to the process of exploitation and applied thoroughly in production to enhance the position of enterprises.

The role of tax rate, average cost, and cheap salary is no longer in a decisive position in the choice of enterprises in the long run. The competition of enterprises in the same field in the new geographical area determines the size and productivity of labor and is a strong driving force for business development. Accordingly, the link between the production networks of many enterprises is an important premise to help limit the problem of asymmetric information between the organizations in the group and commercial banks or informal financial institutions. Shane and Cable, 2002, Straub, 2005; Safavian, M and Wimpey, J, 2007). At the same time, consolidating enterprises in this form also helps to eliminate financial barriers and optimize the quality of enterprises' facilities (Bougheas et al., 2006).

Profits of enterprises tend to decrease in the short term if the company regularly upgrades its human resource strategy, but that helps the business to have a higher position in the financial market. Research by Gnesha Wiganaraja (2001) on the influence of the import of modern technology and equipment on Mauritius textile enterprises in the early 1980s. Thereby, the indicators on business results, import and export of enterprises have shown the level of impact of physical capital on the development of enterprises.

Ignoring the impacts (positive or negative) from foreign direct investment enterprises in Vietnam, it can be said that thanks to the investment of organizations, the quality of physical capital of enterprises has changed. small and medium enterprises in the country. Depending on the level and appropriateness of the business, the positive effects will help businesses in the receiving country improve their physical capital (Fu et al., 2011). Since then, research has pushed the government to expand opportunities for businesses to improve their professional capacity, research and invest in innovation.

The production and business locations of enterprises are opportunities for enterprises to access capital (Gine, 2011). The barriers of doing business vary from country to country, and the difference in financial costs and financing costs also varies between centrally run cities and provinces. Specifically, enterprises in the province often receive informal funding. At the same time, the concentration of businesses in an urban area has the effect of attracting capital and making it easier for businesses to access loans from banks to improve their private facilities. The constant increase in the number of businesses helps commercial banks to collect a huge

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amount of information with accuracy, completeness and integrity, thereby increasing the certainty for the evaluation and decision-making of the businesses. loan bank.

Research Barney (1991), also shows two basic strategies applied to develop: (i) make the best use current short-term capital; and (ii) find and collect new strategic capital in the long term

It can be said that, in the long term, finding and improving technological capabilities and fostering human capacity is the most comprehensive and optimal solution to help businesses maximize their competitive advantages.

Green business opportunities are mostly exploited by small businesses due to the negative effects of the physical-biological environment (Leonidas et al., 2017). From the study of 153 small-scale enterprises in Cyprus, the study shows that the competitive position of enterprises (especially when the industry activities are highly toxic) affects the green business strategy of enterprises.

Not only that, the operational efficiency of an enterprise is also a measure of its goals and plays an important role for managers (Nazarian et al., 2017). Especially, in fact, there are many studies. Research on the causal relationship between traditional culture and folklore (Su and Chen, 2013) but all show that culture affects activities in a stable environment. According to Henri (2006), the corporate culture has a direct impact on the visual efficiency of an enterprise, market orientation and at the same time affects the visual efficiency. If the enterprise owns a strong organizational culture, it will create value for customers and improve service quality in the organization's internal culture. Studies that show an indirect relationship of culture to performance also show similar characteristics.

2.5. The relationship between dynamic capacity and business performance

The performance of an enterprise is recognized as a key concept in management and related fields. At the same time, the definition of corporate performance can be aggregated from the achievements of both departments and corporate organizations (Amin, 2017). Over a certain period of time, the success of an enterprise is closely linked to organizational goals (Lee and Huang, 2012). The concept of corporate governance has a special relationship with the existence and development of enterprises (Ahmed and Shafiq, 2014). Along with that, the operational efficiency of an enterprise can be determined by the level of job completion, the goals of an employee and the successful implementation of the organization's goals (Cascio, 2006). Performance successfully builds business performance with organizational regulations (Rogers, 2016).

“Organizational performance includes effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, quality and innovation” (Tangen, 2004). The corporate governance of a business reflects the success of an organization (Ahmed & Shafiq, 2014). In the Oxford dictionary, operational efficiency is defined as the implementation, application and regular operation based on the commitment between two entities, the relationship between output and input indicates that the operating efficiency has a close relationship with each other. the goal of creating it (Chamanifard, Nikpour, & Chamanifard, 2014). The achievements of enterprises and departments are considered as good governance, which is closely linked to the goals of the enterprise in a particular period (Lee & Huang, 2012).

An effective resource system is made up of dynamic capacity, from which the enterprise integrates, modifies and reshapes its objectives to achieve a competitive advantage for the organization (Ludwig and Pemberton, 2011 cited in (Bleady) and Ali, 2018). At the same time, macro factors are likely to affect the organization. Therefore, with market changes, enterprises need to develop a scenario and prepare carefully and timely, adequate to respond effectively to adversities (Simon et al., 2015).

Not only that, dynamic capacity is applied to ensure the stability of business activities in an organization, affected by changes in technology, policies, administrative procedures and internal management. Next, the true market leaders are those with flexibility and efficiency in the process and control of competitive advantages.

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Based on the studies, it can be affirmed that the concept of organizational culture does not only have direct and indirect effects on the operational efficiency of the organization.

3. Conclusion

Most of the studies have explained and discussed the role of corporate culture in facilitating enterprises to access, maintain and promote their competitive advantages through the use of business theory. resource based. However, the use of theory has not clarified the reason why each individual enterprise develops independently, some industries depend on the development of other industries. For example, improving efficiency and benefiting from the garment industry requires the contribution of the textile industry.

In previous studies, there have been results showing that clan and ethnic culture have a positive impact on the organizational performance of an organization (Acar, 2012). Along with that, research demonstrates that Clan and the Adhocracy Culture have fostered creativity, collaborative innovation to create the optimal environment for businesses. However, the limitation of the study is that the results are not generalized across many disciplines. Based on previous views, very little research exists on the practicality of traditional culture (Maitland et al., 2015). The literature is particularly on the health and wellness industry (Bailey et al., 2017) and is largely geared toward assessing the impact of corporate culture on employees (MacIntosh and Walker, 2012).

According to a large number of previous studies, trust is considered an important organizational culture leading to the success or failure of knowledge management - and also a barrier/motivation in the process of knowledge sharing in corporate culture. However, the inclusion of "trust" as a key factor remains a large gap in research linking organizational culture to organizational culture (Christopian, 2008; Holsapple and Wu, 2008; Salmador and Bueno, 2007; Wu, 2008).

The 4.0 revolution has been changing the landscape of many fields in many industries. The emergence of information technology promotes and emphasizes the important position of the quality of human resources. However, building a financial culture and ensuring the quality of human resources is not easy to grasp immediately and completely. Every organization needs to strive to maximize its capacity and lead the business to sustainable development. Financial culture is closely related to life, a topic that attracts many researches, but there is no effective measure to evaluate the financial culture in an enterprise.

Competitive advantage is the goal of business organizations and is also a positive result of the relationship between the financial culture and the organizational culture, however, the difference depends on the volatile research context (Wollard & Shuck, 2011). The in-depth study of financial culture in many countries is the driving force for businesses to come up with appropriate plans in the process of international integration.

Many studies have shown the relationship between dynamic capacity and the innovation environment, but have not shown the driving factor: organizational culture. Because, corporate culture is openness, willingness to make efforts and effective communication between levels. To create their own cultural identity, many organizations have invested in cultural expression to shape and enhance the cultural image, but many methods have not been effective. The heterogeneous experimental results are the conditions and gaps for further studies to find the relationship of dynamic capacity and the innovation environment,...

Although research on the relationship between the internal and external culture of enterprises has been interested, the perception of enterprises is still vague, which makes the practical application process very difficult. It is perfectly reasonable to consider the cultural culture appropriate to the environment in Vietnam and its own culture. However, the research results have not shown all the characteristics of Vietnamese enterprises. Research often relies on characteristics, advantages, fields and practices to draw conclusions about traditional culture. Meanwhile, the organizational culture environment has not maximized creativity and enthusiasm among employees.

Participating in the signing of many CPTPP, EVFTA, FTA agreements,... optimally shows that our country is strongly integrating and opens up many opportunities for businesses to organize, break barriers and improve financial culture. However, the fierce competition between businesses and organizations presents a difficult problem in terms of retaining talent and limiting brain drain. At the same time, when businesses expand

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their activities to the "multicultural" market, the cultural aspects of the company will become the strength of the business. Many businesses could fall behind in this race if they do not adapt and innovate. So what is an effective solution for Vietnamese enterprises in the process of innovation and integration of the country?

Derived from research gaps and reasons from practice; Especially, from a theoretical perspective, there are still many limitations in terms of perspectives and approaches from research, future research can be carried out as "The influence of financial culture on the performance of textile enterprises".

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